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Institutional Security Management Practices And Quality Public Senior Secondary Schools In Rivers State, Nigeria

Ubakanma, Nkechi Nkiruka¹, Prof. V. C. Onyeike² & Dr. D. S. Osaat³

^{1,2&3}Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Education,
University of Port Harcourt, Choba, Rivers State, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study examined institutional security management practices and quality public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. 2 research questions and 2 null hypotheses guided the study. The study was guided by one theory. The study adopted a correlational survey design. The population comprised 311 (Three hundred and eleven) principals in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample size was 311 principals drawn from the schools using purposive sampling. The instruments used for data collection were two sets of scales titled: “Institutional Security Management Practices Questionnaire (ISMPS)” and “Quality Public Senior Secondary Schools Questionnaire (QPSSSS)”. The two instruments were structured on a four-point modified rating scale. The instruments were validated by two experts in the field of Measurement and Evaluation at, the Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling, of the University of Port Harcourt. Cronbach Alpha Statistics was used to determine the instrument's internal consistency, which yielded the following co-efficient: (ISMPS) and (QPSSSS) were calculated to be 0.83 and 0.80 respectively. The research questions were answered using simple regression, while the hypotheses were tested using a t-test associated with simple regression. The findings of the study revealed that digital surveillance and physical security management predict the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. It was concluded that institutional security management practices had significant predictions on the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommended amongst others that government and non-governmental organizations should provide adequate funds for the installation of digital surveillance security tools in secondary schools.

Keywords: institutional security, management, management practices, quality, public senior secondary schools, and Rivers State.

INTRODUCTION

The educational system can be looked at beyond one's point of view. It could mean different things to different people. In some circumstances, one individual may have more than one understanding of the term educational system. It could in a sense be referring to all formal education institutions responsible for the education of the citizens and others from the earliest/lowest level (nursery, primary to the highest tertiary institution). Educational system can also mean the structuring of educational institutions according to stages. In Nigeria, as in most other countries, education is structured mainly in three (3) stages/levels: (a) primary (b) secondary (c) tertiary levels. The term educational system can be used to denote a policy that structured formal education. Abraham (2013) opined that the educational system is

important because it is through education (social service) that every nation equips the generation of its citizens with acceptable norms, knowledge, skills, and competencies for their survival and for the development of society itself.

Quality education sharpens the minds of citizens, equipping them to transform societies economically, socially, and politically. At significant points in human and national development, challenges in educational development keep emerging and if not checked or properly handled, could thwart the potential efforts aimed at attaining sustainable societal advancement and bringing same to a grinding stop. To handle these challenges properly, the provision of qualitative education has always been a handy tool. In the opinion of the researcher as an educational stakeholder, when education, the curative agent of all other sectors faces eminent threatening challenges such as insecurity, failed leadership, corruption, inadequacy of qualified teachers, and lack of funds, what else could cure the curative agent and how? This is indeed the motivation of the researcher.

Observations of the researcher have shown that a lack of respect for the authority of teachers and others in disciplinary acts threatens the teachers and the rights of other students and generally affects the quality of secondary education in Rivers State. This is because teachers are disrespected and abused by both the parents and students in the school and in some cases the principal does not protect their teachers. Increasingly, students are victimized in schools by fellow students, teachers, cultists, and kidnappers. This is further enunciated by the plethora of school violence in some parts of Rivers State. Safe whenever a potentially dangerous situation arises in the school (Haruna, 2022). Van-Jaarsved (2011) identified the following components of institutional security management practices for ensuring school safety as follows: digital surveillance and physical security management practices.

Digital surveillance is a vital aspect of institutional security management and quality public secondary schools in Rivers State. Ashby (2017) posited that video or digital surveillance can be applied in organizations as a monitoring tool to ensure Total Quality Management (TQM), but warned that it should not be used in policing and infringing on fundamental human rights. This scholar observed that the installation of CCTV in the classrooms enables principals to effectively supervise the teaching-learning process. Thus, digital surveillance also known as video, is a device that can be adopted in schools to ensure that quality is maintained.

Physical security management practices are implemented in schools to ensure the safety of lives and property. When physical security practices are correctly and effectively implemented by a school principal, maximum protection will be guaranteed. Physical security measures can be divided into three categories consisting of outside perimeter measures, inner middle perimeter measures, and internal measures. The outside of the school building is normally the perimeter (first line of defense) of the premises such as signs, fences, and other barriers (barricades), lighting, alarms, and patrols. The inner middle ring (inside) is the security measures used within the boundaries of the facility and can include fences and other barriers (walls), alarms, lightening (often with motion detecting capabilities), Close Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras, warning signs, doors, locks, burglar proofing on windows, security staff and access control system. Lastly, the internal physical security measures are found within buildings and include alarms, CCTV cameras, turnstiles, windows and door bars, locks, safes, vaults, protective lighting, and other barriers (such as security gate across a passage (Lombaard & Kole, 2018). These physical security tools are very essential to maintaining security in the school, however, they cannot function without human beings. Hence, the a need for human security management practices.

Statement of the Problem

Commonplace observations of the researcher have shown that despite the importance of school safety, there seems to be an upsurge of violence arising quite rapidly in schools. It seems that a new wave of mayhem in society has not spared the secondary school principals and members of the school management should be on alert all the time to prevent the occurrence of acts of hooliganism to avoid blame for professional negligence. In some schools, students resort to senseless destruction, burning, maiming, raping or even killing those they think are harsh on them. These problems not only endanger students and teachers but also prevent teachers from concentrating on teaching thereby affecting the quality of public secondary schools.

Hence, the problem of the study put in question form is, what is the extent to digital surveillance, and physical security management, independently or jointly predict quality public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study examine the extent institutional security management practices predict the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives sought to:

1. investigate the extent digital surveillance predicts the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. determine the extent physical security management predicts quality public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does digital surveillance predict the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does physical security management predict the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

1. Digital surveillance does not significantly predict the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Physical security management does not significantly predict the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study will be beneficial to secondary school principals in that they will be aware of their roles to ensure that the link between security and opportunity for academic success is known to the community through the Parent Teachers Association meetings, school-based Management Committee meetings and during graduation and prize giving day celebrations among others. This is because the study would identify the security management practices needed for a quality and stable academic environment.

Delimitations of the Study

This study was delimited in terms of geographical scope and the content scope. The geographical scope of the study was delimited to public secondary schools in Rivers State while the content scope was delimited to the components of the independent variable which are: digital surveillance and physical security management.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Security

Security is the state of being free from danger or threats; freedom from doubt, anxiety, or fear. Security in the school system is the process used to attain tolerable levels of risk in the school environment and safety refers to a long-lasting security program that is well administered. Ike (2015) viewed security as something that gives or assures safety. According to Rogers (2019), security can broadly be defined as a means of providing effective levels of protection against pure risk. It is a process used to create a relatively crime-free area. Security aims to assess the vulnerability to risk and thereafter employ techniques and measures to reduce that vulnerability to a reasonable level. Security will therefore assist in creating a stable, fairly predictable environment in which individuals may move freely with reduced or without any disturbance or injury (Kole & Lambaard, 2018).

Ken (2018) defined security as a condition that results from the establishment and maintenance of protective measures that ensure a state of inviolability from hostile acts or influences. Security can also be explained as a state of care of mind, freedom from doubt, and absence of worry. It can be likened to watching over an organization for an anticipated event. School security management practices can be defined as measures taken for the protection of the students, staff, property, and other school valuable assets from attacks or dangers. According to Kurtus (2012), it is a plan by administrators or principals“ to protect students and staff in the event of danger. It is a plan against criminal and anti-social behavior that can disrupt the work of the school, physical and mental damage to the people, and damage to the school

building (Ragozzino, et al, 2019). School security can also be explained as those measures taken to protect and manage school violence, reduce safety risks and liability, and improve school-community relationships (Trump, 2010). It is the physical protection of school property, school personnel, and students from hostile acts or influences. They are measures taken to maintain order, and discipline, and prevent disruption to the entire school (Fukumi, 2018).

Concept of Management

For a school to efficiently realize its goals, it must have good managers (administrators). According to Davies (2018), management could be seen as a set of activities that involves planning, organizing, leading, and controlling to use of available resources to achieve a desired outcome most efficiently. Peter (2015) however saw management as a process concerned with the formulation of strategies, plans, policies, and programs to achieve set organizational goals. Mandolin (2019) on the other hand viewed management as the instrument to accomplish tasking specified individuals. Onyema (2017) moreover saw management as a set of activities that involves planning, organizing, commanding, coordinating, and controlling in other to achieve defined goals.

Management is a vital function of school administration. The school principal has to plan, organize, direct, control, and evaluate the staff and the material resources to achieve the objective of the school (Obegbulem, 2011). Ike (2015) defined management as the social or international process involving a sequence of coordinated events such as planning, organizing, coordinating, and controlling to use of available resources to achieve the desired outcome in the fastest and most efficient way. School security management practices involve the mobilization and utilization of material resources to attain educational goals. School management is the identification of the school objectives, mobilizing the teachers, academic staff, students, and material resources such as funds, equipment, and facilities in the school to achieve the goal of teaching and learning (Ike, 2015). It is the process of creating a supportive environment by deciding in advance how to secure the school, how to do it, and who is to do it. This includes maintaining, comparing, and correcting towards achieving the school goal (Odufowowu, 2011). Public secondary schools are managed by a principal and vice principal.

Concept of Security Management Practices

Security management can be defined as measures taken by an organization or government to prevent espionage, sabotage, or attack. Security management can also be defined as measures adopted by a business or homeowner to prevent crime, assault, and to prevent escape (Picarell, 2018). Van Jaarsveld (2011) defined security management are a fundamental element that should be implemented in all schools to prevent and reduce school violence as much as possible. Rogers (2019), believed that security management can broadly be defined as a means of providing effective levels of protection against pure risks. Security management is a process used to create a relatively crime-free area. He viewed school security management as the process of creating a conducive and proper internal environment in the school. Trump (2010), security management practices are strategies and procedures required to coordinate the diverse activities of the institution to achieve safety. Security management practices are a valuable and helpful resource to be used in the school environment to achieve safety in school. Thus, security management practices are those measures put in place by the school to ensure the safety of students, properties, facilities, staff, and other stakeholders in the school system.

Mentiki (2012) opined that school security management practices are the steps taken to secure the learners both physically and psychologically by the use of various assigned security awareness programs and strategies. Laura (2014) averred that school security management is a way of providing security technologies and strategies that can be used to mitigate the formidable security threats in the school. It involves plans or measures to be taken to protect and manage school violence, reduce security risks, and ensure that the school environment is safe for learning. Van Jaarsveld (2011) presented five security management practices for ensuring school safety. They include school security risk assessment/analysis management practices, physical security management practices, human security management practices, technological security management practices, and school policies and procedures on security. School security management practices are made up of different components, namely security aids, security measures, policies and procedures, risk assessments, risk analysis, and risk control measures. Security

management practices comprise both physical security and human elements. These in turn are combined to develop and implement a security measure. In brief, security measures are those pieces of equipment or manpower used to improve or add to the overall security system which is made up of several security aids (Mentiki, 2012). Thus, security management practices are defined as measures put in place to stall security threats inherent in a school environment. Security management practices involve the use of school security management procedures, and physical, human, and technological measures to ensure school safety.

Digital surveillance and quality public secondary schools

The nexus between digital surveillance and quality public secondary schools in Rivers State cannot be overemphasized. This importance is supported by Ashby (2017) who opined that video or digital surveillance can be applied in organizations (schools) as a monitoring tool to ensure Total Quality Management (TQM), but warned that it should not be used in policing and infringing on fundamental human rights. The above author further stated that the installation of CCTV in the classrooms enables principals to effectively supervise the teaching-learning process. Thus, digital surveillance also known as video, is a device that can be adopted in schools to ensure that quality is maintained.

Empirical evidence has revealed that installations of CCTV cameras in classrooms in this technological age have proven a veritable tool for monitoring what goes on in the classrooms. The study of Bekker, Hartley, and Daves (2019) has proven that surveillance cameras can offer quality security management in the school environment. Also, Mgadla (2016) discovered that the installation of CCTV cameras in classrooms helped principals to manage emergencies. Thus, effective teaching and learning can take place only in a safe and secure environment. In a related study that was conducted by Naidu and Mhlongo (2018) in South Africa, it was discovered that CCTV cameras in secondary schools monitor learner's behavior because numerous principals had received horrific reports of learners bringing alcohol and weapons into the premises of various schools, as well as reports of learners sexually harassing others. In another study, Venter (2016) observed that teaching and learning were not carried out in classes until school stakeholders raised concerns about the attitude of teachers and revamped the public schools with the installation of CCTV cameras in classrooms. Observations of the researcher have shown that the adoption of CCTV in Rivers State public secondary schools will enable school managers to eradicate mass cheating during examinations. Thus, it will equally enable school managers to be present everywhere at the same time and also keep records of every activity.

Accordingly, in a study conducted by Jeannine (2013), it was found that reviewing the CCTV footage with teachers can encourage them to evaluate their teaching methods while striving to provide the best learning environment possible for their students. This statement is in line with Armitage (2012) who conducted a study that revealed that the application of digital surveillance in the school system helped school managers to monitor students' behavior, know the class that is not learning when it is supposed to, and know teachers who are either under or over-utilized. In another related study, Bates (2018) discovered that with the presence of CCTV cameras, discipline can be easily achieved. Hence, whenever one knows that one's activities are being monitored closely, he or she will learn how to behave well and do the right things at the right time.

Physical Security Management and Quality Public Secondary Schools

Evidence abounds that physical security management practices are implemented in schools to ensure the safety of lives and property. When physical security practices are correctly and effectively implemented by the school principal, maximum protection will be guaranteed. Physical security measures can be divided into three categories consisting of outside perimeter measures, inner middle perimeter measures, and internal measures. The outside of the school building is normally the perimeter (first line of defense) of the premises such as signs fences and other barriers (barricades), lighting, alarms, and patrols. The inner middle ring (inside) is the security measures used within the boundaries of the facility and can include fences and other barriers (walls), alarms, lightning (often with motion detecting capabilities), Close Circuit Television (CCTV) cameras, warning signs, doors, locks burglar roofing on windows, security staff and access control system. Lastly, internal physical security measures are found within buildings and include alarms, CCTV cameras, turnstiles, windows and door bars, locks safes, vaults,

protective lighting, and other barriers (such as security gates across a passage (Lombaard and Kole, 2018). These physical security tools are very essential to maintaining security in the school, however, they cannot function without human beings.

Van-Jaarsveld (2011) states that some physical security management practices for ensuring school safety include maintaining a clean and attractive school, analysis of crime patterns in the areas; knowing staff needs to feel safe and secure; ensuring restricted access to the school and restrictions on scholar attire and possessions clean, attractive schools tend to create a sense of pride to the scholars, educators, parents and the community. This produces attitudes and behavior that are beneficial to the school as a whole, thus discouraging undesirable behavior (Ike, 2018). If a school has broken windows, litter, and/or deteriorating buildings, then it creates the idea that this kind of behavior and image is acceptable. More individuals will then leave litter lying around and graffiti will also be more likely to occur unrestricted or unsanctioned (Van-Jaarsveld, 2011). The school will also then be perceived as being vulnerable, making crime on its premises more likely to occur.

Analysis of crime patterns is important for school principals to continually gather, analyze, and evaluate all kinds of information such information may include attendance rates, suspension and expulsion patterns, tardiness, graduation rates, and crime patterns (including incident management of acts not necessarily deemed 'criminal' but do involve elements of violence or conflict). Schools should have a security plan in place of which an important aspect should be the collection and recording in a register, which can take the form of database incident management program software lending itself to trends, modes of operandi, and spatial analysis of violent incidents.

Theoretical Framework

This study will be guided by the Chaos theory by Douglas Kiel (1993). Chaos Theory was propounded by Douglas Kiel in (1993). According to the theory, chaos is one possible result of the dynamics of nonlinear systems. Kiel explained that there are three fundamental methods for controlling chaos. One of the methods is to alter the parameters of the system. Altering the parameter means limiting the degrees of freedom on the extent of the behavior available to a system. A second method involves perturbations or disturbances during chaotic episodes to change behavior back to more predictable and smoother functioning. The third method aims at altering the orbit of a chaotic system to a more desirable orbit on its attractor. This approach uses continuous tracking and seeks to identify changes in the system behavior that occur over time. Public managers (including principals) work within an environment of considerable constraints. Budget constraints dictate levels of agency services and response. Many school administrators, despite being aware of the need for safety equipment in their schools are not able to provide these requirements because of financial constraints.

In this study, the school is a nonlinear system where issues of safety are characterized by uncertainty, unpredictability, and thus the need for safety measures and preparedness for such eventualities. Chaos widens the spectrum of opinion and forces the organization to seek new points of view. The many incidents of insecurity in schools have increased the need for the adoption of security management practices that should be implemented in schools to enhance safety. About this study, certain measures need to be put in place, to alter the behavior of learners and limit their freedom thus enhancing stability in the school. The measures that may be put in place include fencing of the school compound, inspection of students' lockers, and wearing of school uniforms among others.

The relevance of this theory to the present study is that it emphasizes the need for workplace rules such as policies and work processes on safety. Safety policies are very important because they help to give direction on what should be done to mitigate and respond to a crisis in schools. Principals should know that any effective strategy must consider all relevant stakeholders impacted by the strategic plan.

METHODOLOGY

The design that was adopted in this study was the correlational design. The population of this study consisted of the 311 principals in all the three hundred and eleven (311) public senior secondary schools in the 23 Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The sample of this study was 311 principals who were

the respondents for the study from public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. A purposive sampling technique was used in determining the sample size. The instruments that were used in collecting data for this study were two scales. The first scale was titled ‘Institutional Security Management Practices Scale’ (ISMPS) and the second one was ‘Quality Public Senior Secondary Schools Scale’ (QPSSSS). The items were scaled using the modified four-point Likert-type rating of Very High Extent (4 points), High Extent (3 points), Low Extent (2 points), and Very Low Extent (1 point). The researcher validated the two instruments titled ‘Institutional Security Management Practices Scale’ (ISMPS) and ‘Quality Public Senior Secondary Schools Scale’ (QPSSSS) by subjecting them to the scrutiny of her supervisor and two other experts in the field of Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling in the Faculty of Education of the University of Port Harcourt. The reliability of the instruments was established using the Cronbach Alpha method. The reliability coefficient of the (ISMPS) and (QPSSSS) were calculated to be 0.83 and 0.80 respectively while the reliability coefficient of each variable was 0.82, and 0.81, which showed that the scores were high and the instrument was very reliable. The researcher administered the 311 copies of the instrument to the respondents. 311 copies of the instruments were administered, but 296 copies were correctly filled and were retrieved which represented a 95.1% return rate. Simple regression was used to answer the research questions while a t-test associated with simple regression was used to test hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance using SPSS.

RESULT

Research Question 1: *To what extent does digital surveillance predict the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent Digital Surveillance Predict Quality Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Coefficient of determinism	Decision
1	.715 ^a	.511	.509	51.1%	high extent

Data in Table 1 presents the summary of simple regression analysis on the extent digital surveillance predicts the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. With the model as 1, the regression scores came out as .715^a, the regression square as .511 the adjusted regression square was .509 and the coefficient of determination remained at 51.1%. When reference is made to the scale of measurement, 51.1% falls between 51-75% (high extent). Hence, judging by the coefficient of determinism, it shows that digital surveillance predicted the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State by 51.1%, while the remaining 48.9% was accounted for by other variables.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does physical security management predict the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis on the Extent Physical Security Management Predict Quality Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Coefficient of determinism	Decision
1	.720 ^a	.518	.516	51.8%	high extent

Data in Table 2 presents the summary of simple regression analysis on the extent physical security management predicts the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. With the model as 1, the regression scores came out as .720^a, the regression square as .518 the adjusted regression square was .516 and the coefficient of determination remained at 51.8%. When reference is made to the scale of measurement, 51.8% falls between 51-75% (high extent). Hence, judging by the coefficient of determinism, it shows that physical security management predicted quality public senior secondary schools in Rivers State by 51.8 %, while the remaining 48.2% was accounted for by other variables.

Hypothesis 1: Digital surveillance does not significantly predict the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Table 3: Summary of t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Digital Surveillance Significantly Predicts Quality Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	32.951	.073		42.374	.000
1 Digital surveillance	.104	.029	.715	3.236	.000

Data in Table 3 presents the summaries of the t-test associated with simple regression on the prediction of digital surveillance on quality public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The t- t-calculated value used in testing the hypothesis came out as 3.236, the significant value remained at 0.000 with an alpha value of 0.05. At 0.05 alpha level and t- the observed value of 3.236, the value of the t-test associated with simple regression was 42.374 at the significant value of 0.000 which was less than the alpha value of 0.05. This suggests a significant prediction of the independent variable (digital surveillance) on the dependent variable (quality public senior secondary schools). On this note, the null hypothesis was rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis that, there is a significant prediction of digital surveillance on quality public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: Physical security management does not significantly predict the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

Table 4: Summary of t-test Associated with Simple Regression on the Extent Physical Security Management Significantly Predicts Quality Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	22.631	.055		12.554	.000
1 Physical security management	.221	.018	.720	4.271	.000

Data in Table 4 presents the summaries of the t-test associated with simple regression on the prediction of physical security management on quality public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The t- t-calculated value used in testing the hypothesis came out as 4.271, the significant value remained at 0.000 with an alpha value of 0.05. At 0.05 alpha level and t- the observed value of 4.271, the value of the t-test associated with simple regression was 12.554 at the significant value of 0.000 which was less than the alpha value of 0.05. This suggests a significant prediction of the independent variable (physical security management) on the dependent variable (quality public senior secondary schools). On this note, the null hypothesis was rejected in favor of the alternative hypothesis that, there is a significant prediction of physical security management on quality public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

Digital Surveillance and Quality Public Senior Secondary Schools

The first finding of the study revealed that digital surveillance predicted the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State by 51.1%. It showed a high extent This showed that digital surveillance to an extent predicted the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Digital surveillance in schools offers opportunities for remote observation and the production of recorded evidence This is in

agreement with Ashby (2017) who stated that video or digital surveillance can be applied in organizations (schools) as a monitoring tool to ensure Total Quality Management (TQM). When there are security cameras in schools, they ensure that there is ample security in schools, and help reduce incidences of crime rates. Security, they say is everyone's business; hence the need to ensure that schools are well-guarded with surveillance gadgets. This also agrees with the view of Bekker, Hartley, and Daves (2019), who believed and have proven that surveillance cameras can offer quality security management in the school environment.

Physical Security Management and Quality Public Senior Secondary Schools

The second finding of the study revealed that physical security management predicted the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State by 51.8%. It showed a high extent. This to an extent indicated that physical security management predicted quality public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This corroborates with Van-Jaarsveld (2011) who stated that physical security management practices are that part of security that one can see. Physical security management is implemented as a security measure to ensure the safety measures are implemented correctly and effectively, it will ensure maximum protection. Physical security measures form a part of an integrated security system and should not be used on their own. Building a fence around the school premises, installing burglary bars on all windows in the school premises, installing iron doors in the classrooms, and providing for appropriate security lighting system in and around the school premises are good physical security management measures and practices. These physical security tools are very essential to maintaining security in the school, however, they cannot function without human beings.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that institutional security management practices (digital surveillance and physical security management) all had significant predictions on the quality of public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This implies that the way these practices are implemented can significantly influence the quality of public senior secondary schools, which cannot be taken for granted. The argument is that if they are related, then public senior secondary school principals should wake up to their responsibilities without further delay.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Government and non-governmental organizations should provide adequate funds for the installation of digital surveillance security tools in secondary schools. This can be done through the provision of security grants and aid to secondary schools.
2. The state government through the State Ministry of Education, should ensure the provision of more physical security management infrastructures and tools for secondary school safety.

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